

Lexical Thresholds in Medical English II: AI-Assisted Text Simplification and Its Relationship on Vocabulary and Reading Comprehension

Evgeni Stanchev

Abstract

This study explores how AI-assisted text simplification may influence the relationship between medical vocabulary knowledge and reading comprehension in English for Medical Purposes (EMP). Building on a previous phase, the study adopts a two-group design within a single cohort of 84 second-year medical students, comparing performance on original and simplified versions of the same biochemistry texts. The simplified texts were generated using ChatGPT. Participants completed a 45-item test consisting of 25 vocabulary recognition items and 20 reading comprehension questions. The analysis focuses on overall performance, the relationship between lexical knowledge and comprehension, and the extent to which learners appear to transfer vocabulary knowledge to reading tasks.

The results suggest generally high levels of performance in the AI-assisted condition, with mean scores of 91% for vocabulary and 84% for comprehension. A positive relationship was observed between vocabulary knowledge and comprehension ($r = .74$). When compared with the original-text condition ($r = .56$), this pattern may indicate a somewhat stronger alignment between lexical knowledge and comprehension under simplified conditions. Transfer-efficiency results ($M = 0.92$) suggest that students were generally able to apply their lexical knowledge in reading, although with notable individual variation. At the same time, differences in performance between texts remained, suggesting that text-related factors may continue to play a role even under simplified conditions.

Keywords:

English for Medical Purposes; lexical coverage; vocabulary knowledge; reading comprehension; AI-assisted learning

Introduction

Recent research in second language (L2) reading has increasingly emphasized the importance of lexical coverage as a key factor underlying comprehension, particularly in specialized domains such as English for Medical Purposes (EMP). Rather than supporting the notion of a fixed lexical “threshold,” recent evidence suggests that comprehension tends to improve gradually as the proportion of known words increases, with effective reading typically occurring within a high-coverage range (e.g., 90–98%), depending on text type and learner characteristics (Song & Reynolds, 2022; Pellicer-Sánchez et al., 2024). Within this framework, receptive vocabulary knowledge—the ability to recognize and understand words in context—has been identified as an important predictor of reading performance, often more strongly associated with comprehension than productive vocabulary knowledge (Tong et al., 2023).

In specialized contexts such as medical education, lexical demands are particularly salient. Students are required to process dense, content-rich texts containing a high proportion of domain-specific terminology. In such cases, comprehension may depend not only on general language proficiency but also on the ability to recognize key technical terms. This is especially relevant in English-medium medical instruction, where learners often possess prior conceptual knowledge in their first language and must map that knowledge onto

English lexical forms. Previous research has suggested that limited knowledge of core terminology can disrupt comprehension, even when the underlying concepts are familiar (Song & Reynolds, 2022; Pellicer-Sánchez et al., 2024).

The first phase of the present study (Stanchev, 2026) examined this relationship in a cohort of second-year medical students at MU Varna reading authentic biochemistry texts in English. The findings indicated generally high levels of performance, with mean scores of approximately 93% for vocabulary recognition and 88% for reading comprehension. A moderate positive correlation ($r = .56$) was observed between lexical knowledge and comprehension, suggesting that vocabulary knowledge played an important, though not exclusive, role in reading success. In addition, a transfer-efficiency measure suggested that students were generally able to apply their lexical knowledge during reading, albeit with some individual variation. Taken together, these findings were broadly consistent with the view that lexical coverage may be better understood as a functional range rather than a strict threshold, with approximately 90–93% recognition of targeted domain-specific vocabulary in this study appearing sufficient under conditions of prior content familiarity (Stanchev, 2026).

While these findings contribute to an understanding of lexical processing in EMP contexts, they also raise questions regarding the role of textual difficulty and linguistic accessibility. One possible way to address lexical and processing barriers is through text simplification, which aims to reduce linguistic complexity while preserving core content. Advances in large language models (LLMs), such as ChatGPT, have made it possible to generate simplified versions of specialized texts with increasing fluency and coherence. Recent work in language education has pointed to the potential of such tools to support comprehension by reducing cognitive load and improving accessibility (Zolfaghari et al., 2025). However, empirical evidence on how AI-mediated simplification may affect the relationship between vocabulary knowledge and comprehension remains limited.

From a theoretical perspective, simplification may influence reading in multiple ways. By reducing syntactic complexity and clarifying discourse structure, it may free cognitive resources for meaning construction, in line with accounts of processing efficiency in L2 reading (Pellicer-Sánchez et al., 2024). At the same time, simplification may alter the distribution and salience of lexical items, which could strengthen or weaken the role of vocabulary knowledge as a predictor of comprehension. It therefore remains unclear whether simplified texts primarily make reading easier overall, or whether they change the relationship between lexical knowledge and comprehension.

The present study constitutes the second phase of this line of research and addresses this issue by broadly replicating the original design with a new cohort of medical students, using AI-simplified versions of the same biochemistry texts. By maintaining the same structure—targeted vocabulary assessment, reading comprehension tasks, and a transfer-efficiency measure—the study enables a comparison between the original and simplified conditions.

The study is guided by the following research questions:

1. How well do students perform overall when reading simplified medical texts?
2. To what extent does vocabulary knowledge relate to comprehension under simplified conditions?
3. To what extent do students appear to transfer their lexical knowledge into understanding when reading simplified texts?

By comparing the results of the two phases, the study aims to explore whether AI-driven text simplification is associated with differences in overall comprehension, changes in the strength of the vocabulary–comprehension relationship, or variation in the extent to which learners apply their lexical knowledge

during reading. In doing so, it contributes to ongoing discussions of lexical coverage, processing efficiency, and the potential role of AI tools in specialized L2 reading contexts.

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Results

The AI-assisted cohort consisted of 84 second-year medical students who completed the same 45-item instrument used in the first phase of the study. Overall performance was high. On the full test, students obtained a mean score of 39.69 out of 45, with a median of 41, a standard deviation of 5.25, and a score range from 14 to 45. In proportional terms, this corresponds to an average accuracy of 88.2%. Although performance was generally strong, the wider spread of scores indicates greater variability across students than in the first phase.

Performance on the vocabulary section remained high. On the 25-item lexical recognition test, students achieved a mean score of 22.82, with a median of 23, a standard deviation of 2.45, and scores ranging from 10 to 25. This represents an average accuracy of 91.3%. The distribution suggests that most students recognized a large proportion of the targeted terms, although a smaller subset showed weaker lexical knowledge.

Reading comprehension results were also strong, though slightly lower than vocabulary performance. On Text 1, students achieved a mean score of 8.70 out of 10, with a median of 9, a standard deviation of 1.89, and scores ranging from 2 to 10. This corresponds to a proportional mean of 87%. On Text 2, performance was somewhat lower, with a mean of 8.17, a median of 9, a standard deviation of 2.01, and a range from 2 to 10, yielding a proportional mean of 81.7%. When the two texts were combined, the mean comprehension

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score was 16.87 out of 20, or 84.4% overall. As in the first phase, Text 2 proved more demanding than Text 1.

The relationship between lexical knowledge and reading comprehension was stronger in the AI-assisted cohort than in the first phase. Correlation analysis showed a moderate-to-strong positive relationship ($r = .74$) between vocabulary scores and combined comprehension scores. This indicates that students with better recognition of the target vocabulary also tended to perform better on the reading tasks.

To examine how effectively students applied their lexical knowledge during reading, a transfer-efficiency measure was calculated. The mean transfer-efficiency score was 0.92, with a median of 0.955, a standard deviation of 0.16, and values ranging from 0.48 to 1.32. These results show that students were generally able to convert vocabulary knowledge into reading comprehension, although the wide range suggests considerable individual variation in how efficiently this transfer occurred.

Measure	Mean	Median	Min	Max	SD
Word Score (max 25)	22.82	23	10	25	2.45
Word Score (%)	91	92	40	100	10
Text 1 Score (max 10)	8.70	9	2	10	1.89
Text 1 Score (%)	87	90	20	100	19
Text 2 Score (max 10)	8.17	9	2	10	2.01
Text 2 Score (%)	82	90	20	100	20
Combined Text Score (%)	84	90	20	100	17
Transfer Efficiency	92	95.5	48	132	16
Vocabulary–Comprehension Correlation	0.74	-	-	-	-

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics for Vocabulary and Reading comprehension

Note: Scores for vocabulary and comprehension are reported both as raw totals and proportion correct. Transfer efficiency represents the ratio of comprehension performance to vocabulary knowledge. Correlation represents Pearson's r between vocabulary and combined comprehension scores.

Figure 1. Performance of second-year medical students on vocabulary and reading comprehension tasks under AI-assisted text simplification. Scores are shown as percentages for word recognition (Word Score), comprehension for Text 1 and Text 2, combined comprehension (Combined Text), and transfer efficiency, representing the extent to which vocabulary knowledge was applied during reading.

Overall, the AI-assisted cohort demonstrated high performance across vocabulary and comprehension tasks, a strong relationship between lexical knowledge and understanding, and generally effective transfer of vocabulary knowledge into reading, albeit with notable differences between individual students and between the two texts.

Discussion

The results of this study provide insight into how AI-assisted text simplification relates to reading comprehension and vocabulary knowledge in English for Medical Purposes (EMP). By comparing a single cohort of students across original and simplified texts, we can examine not only performance outcomes but also how comprehension depends on lexical knowledge under different text conditions.

Overall, students in the AI-assisted condition demonstrated high levels of performance on both vocabulary recognition and reading comprehension tasks. Performance was slightly lower than in the original-text condition in some respects, indicating that simplification does not automatically lead to higher comprehension scores. Rather, simplification appears to influence how comprehension is achieved.

A key observation emerges from the relationship between vocabulary knowledge and comprehension. In the original-text condition (Stanchev, 2026), the correlation was moderate ($r = .56$), suggesting that while vocabulary knowledge contributed to comprehension, other factors—such as syntactic complexity,

discourse organization, or inferencing demands—also played a role. In the simplified-text condition, this correlation increased to $r = .74$, indicating a stronger alignment between vocabulary knowledge and comprehension.

This pattern can be understood more clearly by considering the nature of simplification. Simplifying the text reduces obstacles such as complex sentence structures, difficult syntax, and dense discourse organization. By removing these non-lexical sources of difficulty, the simplification process leaves students' knowledge of target vocabulary as the primary remaining challenge. In other words, with the other barriers "faded away," comprehension depends almost entirely on whether students recognize and understand the key terms. Students who know the vocabulary can read with minimal interference from structural or organizational difficulties, while students who lack vocabulary struggle despite the simpler language.

Importantly, text simplification does not eliminate all barriers to comprehension. Students who lack knowledge of the target vocabulary are unlikely to benefit substantially from shorter or simpler sentences. In other words, simplification does not teach unknown words; it only removes other sources of difficulty, such as complex syntax or dense discourse structure. Its effect is therefore greatest for learners who already possess some or most of the relevant vocabulary, allowing them to read more efficiently and apply their lexical knowledge more directly. For beginners or low-vocabulary students, comprehension remains constrained by the words they do not know, regardless of how simple the sentences are.

The transfer-efficiency measure supports this interpretation. Students were generally able to apply their vocabulary knowledge effectively when reading simplified texts, with individual variation reflecting differences in reading strategies, inferencing ability, or engagement. Notably, Text 2 remained slightly more challenging than Text 1 even after simplification, suggesting that some text-internal factors, such as conceptual density or informational complexity, continue to influence comprehension independently of vocabulary.

Taken together, these findings suggest that AI-assisted simplification does not uniformly make reading easier; rather, it changes the landscape of difficulty. By reducing non-lexical challenges, simplification allows vocabulary knowledge to play a clearer, more direct role in comprehension. This supports the view of lexical coverage as a functional range rather than a fixed threshold: when learners have sufficient subject knowledge, recognizing approximately 90% or more of the relevant vocabulary appears sufficient to support comprehension, even in specialized medical texts.

In practical terms, this means that AI tools for text simplification can be understood not merely as instruments to reduce overall difficulty, but as interventions that selectively remove barriers and clarify which factors—here, vocabulary knowledge—actually drive understanding. This has implications for both teaching and assessment, highlighting the importance of targeted vocabulary instruction alongside any text adaptation strategies.

Limitations

Several limitations should be considered when interpreting the findings of this study.

First, the study compared two halves of the same medical cohort under different conditions. While this approach helps maintain a broadly comparable academic context, the assignment was not fully randomized at the individual level. As a result, some pre-existing differences in English proficiency or vocabulary knowledge cannot be entirely excluded, particularly given the varied educational backgrounds of the students, including those with prior intensive English-language instruction.

Second, the sample was intentionally content-homogeneous, as all participants had previously completed coursework in biochemistry and were therefore familiar with the subject matter. This supports the interpretation that differences in performance are more likely to be language-related rather than conceptual. At the same time, it may limit the extent to which the findings generalize to learners without comparable domain-specific knowledge.

Third, the study examined the effects of a single instance of AI-assisted text simplification. The simplification was guided by prompts instructing the model to reduce syntactic complexity, clarify sentence structure, and preserve key terminology and informational content with the aim of improving accessibility, and the results reflect this particular implementation. The study does not compare different levels of simplification or alternative approaches, and the findings should therefore be interpreted within the context of this specific procedure.

Fourth, ceiling effects were present, particularly in the vocabulary component, where many students achieved near-maximum scores. Although some variability was observed, the generally high level of performance may have reduced the sensitivity of the measures and limited the precision with which relationships between variables could be detected.

Fifth, lexical coverage was operationalized through a selected set of domain-specific items rather than full-text coverage. As such, the reported percentages reflect knowledge of targeted vocabulary rather than the total proportion of known words in the texts.

Finally, the transfer-efficiency measure should be interpreted with caution, as it remains exploratory and has not been independently validated. While it provides an indication of how learners may apply vocabulary knowledge during reading, it may also be influenced by additional factors such as general reading ability or test-taking strategies.

Conclusion

This study examined how AI-assisted text simplification may relate to the relationship between medical vocabulary knowledge and reading comprehension in a cohort of second-year medical students. The results suggest that students were able to maintain relatively high levels of performance when reading simplified biomedical texts, with vocabulary recognition averaging approximately 91% and comprehension approximately 84%.

A comparison with the original-text condition indicates that the relationship between vocabulary knowledge and comprehension may be somewhat stronger under simplified conditions. This pattern may suggest that lexical knowledge plays a more prominent role when certain sources of linguistic complexity are reduced. At the same time, students appeared generally able to apply their vocabulary knowledge during reading, although individual differences remained evident.

Importantly, the findings do not appear to support a straightforward interpretation of AI-based simplification as a means of improving overall comprehension. Rather, they may indicate that simplification is associated with a shift in the balance of factors underlying the reading process, with comprehension becoming more closely aligned with lexical knowledge while still being influenced by text-related and individual variables.

In line with the first phase of the study, the results are broadly consistent with a view of lexical coverage as a functional range rather than a fixed threshold. Recognition of approximately 90% or more of the relevant

domain-specific vocabulary may be sufficient to support comprehension under conditions of prior subject knowledge in medical ESP contexts, particularly when learners possess prior subject knowledge.

Overall, the study contributes to ongoing discussions of vocabulary, processing, and text adaptation in L2 reading, and suggests that AI tools may be understood not only as means of reducing difficulty, but also as factors that can shape the conditions under which comprehension takes place.

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Evgeni Stanchev, PhD Candidate in SHU “K. Preslavski”, Lecturer in MU Varna
Евгени Станчев, докторант към ШУ Е „К. Преславски“, преподавател в МУ Варна
Email: evgeni.stanchev@mu-varna.bg
<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-1108-1067>

Appendix A: Medical Academic Vocabulary List (MAVL):

cell, data, muscular, significant, clinic, analyze, respond, factor, method, protein, tissue, dose, gene,

previous, demonstrate, normal, process, similar, concentrate, function, therapy, indicate, area, obtain research, vary. activate, require, induce, cancer, occur, role, evident, range identify, period, outcome, phase, specific, liver, infect, culture, mediate, score, affect, potential, individual, expose, involve, survive, target respective, intervene, site, per, design, primary, approach, estimate, component, acid, baseline, procedure, overall, pathway, inflammation, region, participate, lesion, technique, volume, serum, define, evaluate, prior, assay, injury, section, task, achieve, symptom, detect, molecular, error, incubate, donor, intense, chronic, fraction, insulin, contrast, react, source, available, disorder, positive, structure, multiple generate, conclude, medium, inhibit, complex, distribute, major, tumor, initial, channel, receptor, membrane, stress, strain, nuclear, ration, approximate, release, transparent, surgery, assess, impact, versus, drug, laboratory, minimize, reveal, scan, monitor, criterion, visual, duration, cycle, investigate, acute, sequence, select, maximize, whereas, peak, elevation, image, enzyme, parameter, isolate, mutation, enhance, calcium, glucose, appropriate, incidence, conduct, protocol, background, stimulate, algorithm, establish, efficacy, hypothesis, feature, internal, mortality, array, derive, series, buffer, specimen, focus, display, plasma, abstract, grade, secondary, strategy, graft, undergo, peripheral, transcription, despite, consist, status, furthermore, immune, reverse, infuse, author, interact, issue, negative, throughout, goal, vein chamber, independent, proliferation, formation, subsequent, predict, correspond, correlate, regulate, exclude, metabolic, device, recruit, final, impair, inject, percent, publish, remove, syndrome, exhibit, blot, defect, biopsy, index, diameter, cognitive, followup, fluid, lipid, magnetic, margin, energy, locate, survey, software, profile, attribute, convention, synthesis, recover, objective, filter, segment, compound, link, guideline, extract, proportion, regression, questionnaire, discharge, respiratory, gender, summary, promote, tract, toxic, relevant, episode, acquire, communicate, internal, dimension, layer, microscope, adverse, recipient, density, virus, interpret, document, instruct, oral, theory, illustrate, probe, diagnose, consequence, version, create, dilute, skeletal, novel, threshold, technology, element, dynamic, challenge, typical, transfer, aspect, diet, cohort, external, vector, antibiotic, domain, temporary, linear, plus, digit, accurate, concept, transport, rotate, input, absorb, replicate, distinct, radical, superior, contact, ensure, stable, prevalence, capture, degrade, anesthesia, optimal, kit, bias, proximal, constant, incorporate, sufficient, sustain, label, barrier, zone, chart, implement, trauma, find, context, hence, community, lateral, facilitate, trim, prolong, quantify, perception, accumulate, expert, grant, amplification, random, construct, mount, renal, environment, couple, laser, magnitude, formula, deficit, alter, access, supplement, eliminate, graph, shift, capacity, qualitative, simulate, globe, modulate, output, attenuate, statistic, prescribe, differentiate, equivalent, orient, practitioner, substantial, chemical, thereby, onset, intake, stance, trend, overnight, contribute, enable, spectrum, assign, option, implicate, aid, tag, portion, electron, cope, decline, species, unique, overlap, adjacent, node, transform, modify, manual, colleague, core, entry, deficient, cascade, benefit, identical, parallel, migrate, reagent, exceed, comprise, highlight, evolution, schedule, organism, predominant, cumulative, purchase, plot, seek, emerge, affinity valid, code, sterile, compute, prospect, utilize, deposit, column, contract, scar, axis, inferior, deviate, trigger, loop, precursor, perceive, preliminary, undertake, substitute, whilst, scenario, adapt, adult, expand, cord, fundamental, feedback, sum, elicit, circulation, tolerance, team, see, candidate, assume, imply, terminal, vascular, hormone, minor, panel, aggressive, comprehensive, residual, perspective, brief, trace, quip, accelerate, template, mode, diminish, consecutive, foundational, emphasize, physiology, oxide, restore, conflict, phenomenon, invade, restrict, attach, longitude, technical, nevertheless, append, infiltrate, bacteria, agonist, rely, capable, manipulate, histology, pharmacology, saline, persist, integrity, precede, rear, mental, demographic, pathology, prominent, apparatus, paradigm, adjust, crucial, nervous, gradient, disrupt, encounter, nitrogen, format, robust, spontaneous, principal, transmit, audit, decade, comprise, cue, gland, assist, inner, intrinsic, consume, suppress, fragment, hypertension, placebo, dominant, text, susceptible, spinal, incorporate, principle, relapse, numerical, resolve, mature, uniform, diverse, retain, abdominal, lane, vital, suspend, voluntary, diffuse, rationale, simultaneous, transient, secrete, methanol, confer, constitute, accomplish, enroll, embryo,

logistic, project, insight, compliance, emission, soluble, comment, oxygen, warrant, route, morbidity, widespread, alcohol, conjugate, acknowledge, alternative, manifest, cluster, notion, render, malignancy, resemble, obvious, antigen, concomitant, fusion, elucidate, consensus, file, biology, urban verify, speculate, postulate, routine, somewhat, catheter, odd, discrete, converse, span, augment, depict, adequate, neutral, thereafter, annual, plastic, professional, recall, entity, precise, successie, ontaminate, tone, integrate, confound, profound, tension, ramatic, blast, encompass, consult, static.

The full Medical Academic Vocabulary List (MAVL) is available at [EAP Foundation](#)

Final 50 MAVL Words for Quiz:

acid; approximate; available; bacteria; buffer; calcium; capable; capacity; cell; chemical; code; conjugate; constant; contract; converse; create; define; dimension; distinct; display; diverse; donor; enzyme; formation; function; hormone; amino; infect; linear; link; obtain; occur; peptide; plasma; predominant; primary; process; protein; react; recall; regulate; release; secondary; species; specific; structure; unique; virus; neutral; target;